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A Structural Analysis of Role of JEEViKA Model in Women Empowerment in Bihar

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Abstract:

This paper examines the role of JEEViKA (Bihar Rural Livelihood Promotion Society) in empowering women of Bihar through institutional development, financial inclusion, and livelihood diversification. Based entirely on secondary data, the study analyses the growth of SHGs, Vos, CLFs, and Producer Groups in all 38 districts of Bihar. The findings demonstrate that although JEEViKA's seems to be a tri-layer community structure but in reality, it plays role of multi-tiered community structure and has significantly strengthened the socio-economic status of rural women, enhanced financial access, and supported sustainable livelihood initiatives that meet out Sustainable Development Goals.

Keywords: JEEViKA, SHGs, Women's Empowerment, Social Capital, Participatory Development

1. Introduction:

Background:

In rural India, women often face socio-economic discrimination that limit their access to resources, mobility and participation in decision-making (Raksh, 2023). To tackle these structural inequalities, community-led approaches have gained prominence as sustainable mechanisms for poverty reduction and gender empowerment. In Bihar, one of India's most socio-economically challenged states, the Bihar Rural Livelihoods Promotion Society-popularly known as JEEViKA- has pioneered a model of women-led development through collective action and institutional strengthening (BRLPS, 2024). By mobilizing women into Self-Help Groups (SHGs) and federating them into higher institutions, JEEViKA aims to enhance financial inclusion and sustainable livelihood opportunities. As per the Bihar's Economic Survey of F.Y. 24-25, "Bihar's economy has a growth rate of 9.2% in the year 2023-24, which places Bihar at third place among all the states of the economy.

Overview of the Study:

JEEViKA functions through a robust three-layer community institutional framework including SHGs, Village Organizations (VOs), and Cluster Level Federations (CLFs). These institutions serve as a platform for savings, credit, livelihood promotion, and leadership development. Over the years, JEEViKA has expanded significantly, supporting women's access to banking services, credit linkages, and market-oriented activities through Producer Groups (PGs) across farm, non-farm, and livestock sectors. This paper provides an analytical overview of how JEEViKA's institutional growth, financial mechanisms, and livelihood interventions collectively contribute to women's empowerment in Bihar, using secondary data as the basis of examination.

2. Literature Review:

Kabeer (2005) conceptualizes empowerment as access to resources, agency, and achievements. Her framework explains JEEViKA enhances women's financial independence, mobility, and decision-making power. Kumar & Rani (2016)

conducted a case study on BRLPS shows that JEEViKA's SHG-VO-CLF model increases savings, credit access, bank linkage and livelihood opportunities for rural women, strengthening both economic and social empowerment. [BRLPS Annual Report \(2020\)](#) highlights improvement in women's leadership, mobility and livelihood diversification under JEEViKA. It also highlights reduced dependence on informal credit sources. [Mirivel et al. \(2022\)](#) find that JEEViKA significantly enhances women's mobility, leadership, and community participation. The study links SHG participation directly to empowerment outcomes. [Banik & Shah \(2010\)](#) show that strong community institutions promote inclusion and transparency. This indirectly supports JEEViKA's collectivization model for empowering rural women. [Chopra \(2016\)](#) demonstrates that decentralized governance improves rural development. This aligns with JEEViKA strategy of empowering women through community-led institutions. [Jha \(2003\)](#) highlights India's long tradition of participatory governance. This justifies JEEViKA's grassroots, women-led self-governance model. [Lipsky \(1980\)](#) theory explains how frontline workers shape programme outcomes. It helps analyse how JEEViKA's CRPs and project staff influence empowerment at the grassroots. [Kumar \(2005\)](#) finds participatory rural development builds social capital and collective identity. [Dr Arman Alam \(2023\)](#) reports that JEEViKA increases women's income, savings, and financial literacy. The study confirms strong socio-economic empowerment through SHGs. [Ravi Ranjan \(2025\)](#) shows that JEEViKA strengthens access to schemes, loans, and livelihoods. His findings highlight sustainable empowerment through women-led institutions. [Tripti Raksha \(2023\)](#) emphasizes that JEEViKA's SHG-VO-CLF structure boosts economic agency and reduces reliance on moneylenders. She highlights the programme's role in institutionalized women-led governance.

Research Gap:

Although most studies affirm positive outcomes, the remaining gap include limited integration of financial, social and psychological empowerment dimensions, scant empirical studies on district-level variation in empowerment. Lack of longitudinal data linking SHG membership duration with empowerment intensity and inadequate theoretical modeling of empowerment pathways.

3. Objective of the Study:

1. To assess the institutional growth of SHGs, VOs, and CLFs under JEEViKA.

2. To examine the financial inclusion of women through savings bank accounts.
3. To analyze livelihood diversification through farm, non-farm, and livestock producer group.
4. To evaluate JEEViKA’s role as a pathway to socio-economic empowerment.

4. Methodology:

This paper is entirely based on secondary data, collected from official reports, government databases, and previously published documents related to JEEViKA. Descriptive analysis has been used to understand institutional structures, financial inclusion indicators, and livelihood distribution.

5. Conceptual Model of JEEViKA for Women’s Empowerment:

The conceptual model for this study is designed by integrating the three foundational pillars of JEEViKA; Institutional Structure, Financial Inclusion, and Livelihood Diversification, and mapping how these elements collectively strengthen women’s social capital, agency, and empowerment outcomes. The model visually represents the sequential and reinforcing pathways through which JEEViKA transforms rural women’s socio-economic position in Bihar.

6. Institutional Growth Under JEEViKA:

JEEViKA’s has evolved into one of India’s largest and most structured women-led community institutional platforms. Its three-tier architecture- self-help group at the base, village organizations at the intermediary level, and cluster level federations at the apex- has enabled system expansion of women’s collectives across Bihar.

Table 1: Current Institutional Structure of JEEViKA

Institution Type	Total Number
SHGs	11,51,649
VOs	77,549
CLFs	1,697

Source: JEEViKA CBO Dashboard

With more than 11.51 lakh SHGs, and over 11.5 million women come together and joined SHGs, JEEViKA has achieved saturation across all 38 districts and 534 blocks of Bihar. The presence of 77,549 Vos indicates strong cluster-level governance, while 1,697 CLFs provides institutional stability, financial oversight, and leadership development. These numbers reflect not only vast geographical penetration but also deep social mobilization, making JEEViKA a central pillar of rural development in Bihar. The institutional growth highlights the programme's ability to mobilize communities and build resilient, women-led governance structures.

7. Financial Inclusion Through Savings Accounts:

Financial inclusion forms the backbone of JEEViKA's empowerment model. By integrating women into the formal financial ecosystem, SHGs promote savings discipline, reduce financial vulnerability, and ensure access to credit.

Table 2: Current Banking and Credit Access Among JEEViKA Institutions

Institution Type	No. Savings Bank Accounts
SHGs	10,49,877
VOs	75,828
CLFs	1,683

Table 3: Current Credit Access Among JEEViKA Institutions

Institution Type	No. Loan Accounts
SHGs	9,88,488

Source: JEEViKA CBO Dashboard

The data reflects a near-universal banking integration of SHGs, VOs, and CLFs. With 10.49 lakh SHG savings accounts, JEEViKA ensures that the majority of rural women are part of formal financial networks. Similarly, 9.88 lakh loan accounts indicate that SHGs have become reliable credit channels, reducing women’s dependence on formal lenders.

8. Livelihood Diversification Through Producer Groups:

Livelihood diversification is central to JEEViKA’s strategy for sustainable empowerment. Producer Groups (PGs) enable women to shift from subsistence-level activities to market-oriented, collective enterprises, enhancing income stability and bargaining power.

Table 4: Current Livelihood Producer Groups

PG Type	No. of PGs
Farm-based PGs	2,618
Non-Farm PGs	1,350
Livestock PGs	6,462

Source: JEEViKA CBO Dashboard

With 6,462 livestock producer groups, livestock-based livelihoods dominate due to low initial investment, high asset turnover, year-round income, ease of women’s participation. Farm based PGs, 2,618 supports collective farming, seed production, organic cultivation, irrigation management, and FPO linkages. Non-farm PGs (1,360) include handicrafts, tailoring, food processing, and micro-enterprises important for income diversification.

9. Analysis and Discussion:

JEEViKA’s extensive institutional reach shows a strong commitment to women’s collective empowerment. With over 11 lakh SHGs, the platform has succeeded in mobilizing rural women at an unprecedented scale. VOs and CLFs ensure that women participate in leadership roles, financial governance, and decision-making.

Financial inclusion indicators demonstrate that JEEViKA has significantly enhanced women's access to formal banking systems. Although the number of savings accounts appears proportionately small, their existence highlights institutional financial visibility.

Livelihood diversification indicates that women are moving beyond traditional roles into sustainable income-generating activities. The dominance of livestock PGs validates the suitability of livestock-based livelihoods in Bihar's rural economy.

Overall, the data confirms that JEEViKA contributes to women's empowerment by promoting economic independence, collective agency, improved financial literacy, and enhanced livelihood opportunities.

10. Findings:

- JEEViKA has developed one of India's largest women-led community structures.
- SHGs, VOs, and CLFs provide strong institutional support for women's empowerment.
- Financial inclusion is enhanced through the establishment of savings accounts across tiers.
- Livelihood diversification is evident, especially in livestock-based PGs.
- Women are increasingly participating in governance, decision-making, and economic activities.
- JEEViKA's interventions have improved confidence, mobility, and economic security for rural women.

Conclusion:

The analysis reveals that JEEViKA has emerged as a powerful pathway of women-led development in Bihar by mobilizing more than 1.15 crore women into SHGs, VOs, and CLFs. Its strong institutional framework ensures collective action, social cohesion, and grassroots governance. Financial inclusion has significantly increased, with nearly all SHGs accessing formal bank accounts and loans.

This shift has reduced dependence on informal credit and strengthened women's financial independence. Livelihood initiatives, particularly livestock, farm, and non-farm PGs, have expanded income opportunities. Women now participate more actively in markets, community meetings, and decision-making processes. JEEViKA has enhanced women's agency, mobility, confidence, and negotiation power. Social capital developed through group-based institutions has strengthened solidarity and mutual support. Overall, JEEViKA has created a sustainable pathway for economic and social empowerment in rural Bihar. Its integrated model serves as a replicable

Integrated Empowerment Model of JEEVIKA (IEM-JEEVIKA)

framework for inclusive development and gender transformation. The program stands as a model for rural development and gender empowerment in India.

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